

Yossi Meystel was born 1975 in Chicago, IL. He is an active supporter of several Illinois-based Jewish organizations, such as Joan Dachs Bais Yaakov, an elementary school in Chicago that provides a high-quality education for nearly 500 students. In addition, Yossi Meystel donates to Agudath Israel of Illinois, a center for Haredi Jews that provides community leadership and official opinions on American policy. He is also involved with the Chicago Center for Torah and Chesed.

He donates heavily to groups such as the Jewish United Fund/Jewish Federation of Metropolitan Chicago (juf.org), a nonprofit organization that connects volunteers who want to help people in need. The organization follows the basic concept of tikkun olam, or repairing the world through community service, action, and social justice. Over the course of his career, Yossi Meystel has also contributed his time and resources to organizations including the Chicago Center for Torah and Chesed, Camp Nageela Midwest, and Madragos.

Mr. Meystel holds a master of business administration with a focus on accounting from Indiana University South Bend. He has authored a number of articles about the stresses involved in the nursing home selection and his insights into the property management industry. This experienced business leader oversaw YAM Management for 8 years, leading the property management group to achieve a 25 percent increase in net earnings within the company's first 5 years. As president of the firm, which maintained 24 elder care nursing facilities, Yossi Meystel spearheaded business development in several key areas, including long-term financial strategies and compliance initiatives. Under his leadership, the Skokie, Illinois, venture provided personalized care to its residents while following a business model emphasizing acquisition, control, accountability, and maintenance.

Outside of his professional obligations, Mr. Meystel is a fan of professional sports, including baseball, basketball, football, and soccer. He is an avid supporter of Chicago's hometown teams, including the Bulls, Cubs, Whitesox, Bears, and Blackhawks. In his spare time, Yossi Meystel also enjoys reading and traveling.